

AI Applications Resource Allocation in Computing Continuum: a Stackelberg Game Approach

Roberto Sala, Hamta Sedghani, Mauro Passacantando, Giacomo Verticale and Danilo Ardagna

Abstract—The growth, development, and commercialization of artificial intelligence-based technologies such as self-driving cars, augmented-reality viewers, chatbots, and virtual assistants are driving the need for increased computing power. Most of these applications rely on Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), which demand substantial computing capacity to meet user demands. However, this capacity cannot be fully provided by users' local devices due to their limited processing power, nor by cloud data centers due to high transmission latency from long distances. Edge cloud computing addresses this issue by processing user requests through 5G, which reduces transmission latency from local devices to computing resources and allows the offloading of some computations to cloud back-ends. This paper introduces a model for a Mobile Edge Cloud system designed for an application based on a DNN. The interaction among multiple mobile users and the edge platform is formulated as a one-leader multi-follower Stackelberg game, resulting in a challenging non-convex mixed integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problem. To tackle this, we propose a heuristic approach based on Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions, which solves the MINLP problem significantly faster than the commercial state-of-the-art solvers (up to 50,000 times). Furthermore, we present an algorithm to estimate optimal platform profit when sensitive user parameters are unknown. Comparing this with the full-knowledge scenario, we observe a profit loss of approximately 1%. Lastly, we analyze the advantages for an edge provider to engage in a Stackelberg game rather than setting a fixed price for its users, showing potential profit increases ranging from 16% to 66%.

Index Terms—Stackelberg game, Mobile Edge Cloud system, DNN partitioning.

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APPENDIX

For the sake of space, we provide proofs of the theorems, details of the functions embedded in the algorithms, and some tables of the experimental results in the following subsections.

Proof of the theorems

In this section, we provide the proofs of the theorems stated in Section 4. We recall that Theorems 4.1 and 4.3 establish the convexity of the response time constraints on the platform side for the single and multiple deployment offloading scenarios, respectively. Theorem 4.2 provides an exact solution to the platform problem for the single deployment offloading scenario, without considering the delay term due to data transfer between edge and cloud. Furthermore, we show that there is no closed-form solution for the problem when including this delay term. Theorems 4.4 and 4.5 estimate the optimal number of edge servers and cloud VMs required to meet user demand and maintain an average response time in the Only Edge and Only Cloud scenarios, respectively. Finally, Theorem 4.6 proves that the maximum of the platform profit function lies at a point of discontinuity or in a left neighborhood of it.

Proof of Theorems 4.1 and 4.3

Proof. We denote the response time of edge resources for deployment k as follows:

$$f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}) = \frac{\lambda_e^{(k)}}{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{D_e^{(k)} n_e^{(k)}}{n_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)}}. \quad (30)$$

The first derivative of f respect to $n_e^{(k)}$ is

$$\frac{\partial f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)})}{\partial n_e^{(k)}} = -\frac{1}{\lambda^{(k)}} \frac{(\lambda_e^{(k)})^2 (D_e^{(k)})^2}{[n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^2}, \quad (31)$$

the first derivative of f respect to $\lambda_e^{(k)}$ is

$$\frac{\partial f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)})}{\partial \lambda_e^{(k)}} = \frac{1}{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{D_e^{(k)} (n_e^{(k)})^2}{[n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^2}. \quad (32)$$

The second derivative of f respect to $n_e^{(k)}$ is

$$\frac{\partial^2 f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)})}{\partial n_e^{(k)2}} = \frac{1}{\lambda^{(k)}} \frac{2(\lambda_e^{(k)})^2 (D_e^{(k)})^2}{[n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^3}, \quad (33)$$

the second derivative of f respect to $\lambda_e^{(k)}$ is

$$\frac{\partial^2 f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)})}{\partial \lambda_e^{(k)2}} = \frac{1}{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{2(D_e^{(k)})^2 (n_e^{(k)})^2}{[n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^3}, \quad (34)$$

and the mixed derivative is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)})}{\partial \lambda_e^{(k)} \partial n_e^{(k)}} &= \frac{\partial^2 f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)})}{\partial n_e^{(k)} \partial \lambda_e^{(k)}} \\ &= -\frac{1}{\lambda^{(k)}} \left(\frac{2\lambda_e^{(k)} (D_e^{(k)})^2 n_e^{(k)}}{[n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^3} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Hence, the Hessian matrix of f is

$$\nabla^2 f(n_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}) = \frac{2(D_e^{(k)})^2}{\lambda^{(k)} [n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^3} \begin{bmatrix} (\lambda_e^{(k)})^2 & -\lambda_e^{(k)} n_e^{(k)} \\ -\lambda_e^{(k)} n_e^{(k)} & (n_e^{(k)})^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (36)$$

Notice that the determinant of the Hessian matrix (i.e., the product of eigenvalues) is equal to zero and the trace of the Hessian matrix (i.e., the sum of the eigenvalues) is equal to

$$\frac{2(D_e^{(k)})^2 [(\lambda_e^{(k)})^2 + (n_e^{(k)})^2]}{[n_e^{(k)} - \lambda_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}]^3} > 0. \quad (37)$$

Hence, the Hessian matrix is positive semi-definite and f is convex. Considering the response time of cloud resources for deployment k , i.e., the function

$$g(n_c^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}) = \frac{\lambda_c^{(k)}}{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{D_c^{(k)} n_c^{(k)}}{n_c^{(k)} - D_c^{(k)} \lambda_c^{(k)}}, \quad (38)$$

the result is analogous. We denote, now, the data transfer time for deployments k as follows:

$$h(n_c^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}) = \frac{\lambda_c^{(k)}}{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{\delta_{II}^{(k)}}{\bar{B}}. \quad (39)$$

The Hessian of h is the null matrix, so its eigenvalues are zeros. Since the response time constraints (25) are the sum of multiple convex functions, they are convex. \square

Proof of Theorem 4.2

Proof. In the following, since the only non-local deployment is \bar{k} , the index (\bar{k}) is omitted. Therefore, $n_e = n_e^{(\bar{k})}$, $n_c = n_c^{(\bar{k})}$, $D_e = D_e^{(\bar{k})}$, $D_c = D_c^{(\bar{k})}$, $\lambda_e = \lambda_e^{(\bar{k})}$, $\lambda_c = \lambda_c^{(\bar{k})}$ and $\lambda = \lambda^{(\bar{k})}$. The edge platform problem, where no cloud resource is used, can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\min c_e n_e \\ &\text{subject to: } n_e \leq N_e \\ &\quad \frac{D_e n_e}{n_e - D_e \lambda} \leq \bar{R} \\ &\quad n_e - D_e \lambda > 0 \end{aligned}$$

that is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} &\min c_e n_e \\ &\text{s.t. } n_e \leq N_e \\ &\quad n_e \geq \frac{\bar{R} D_e \lambda}{\bar{R} - D_e} \end{aligned}$$

whose optimal solution is

$$n_e^* = \frac{\bar{R}D_e\lambda}{\bar{R} - D_e},$$

provided that the feasible region of the latter problem is nonempty, i.e.,

$$\lambda \leq \frac{N_e(\bar{R} - D_e)}{\bar{R}D_e},$$

that is the total load is small enough.

If the total load does not satisfy the above condition, then edge resources are saturated and also cloud resources have to be used. Thus, the edge platform problem is:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{(\lambda_e, n_c)} c_c n_c \\ & \text{s.t. } \frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} + \frac{n_c D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)} \leq \bar{R} \lambda \\ & \quad 0 < \lambda_e < \lambda \\ & \quad N_e - D_e \lambda_e > 0 \\ & \quad n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e) > 0. \end{aligned}$$

The latter problem is convex and standard constraint qualifications hold (e.g., Slater condition is satisfied), hence it is equivalent to the corresponding KKT system:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu_1 \left[\frac{D_e N_e^2}{(N_e - D_e \lambda_e)^2} - \frac{D_c n_c^2}{(n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e))^2} \right] \\ & \quad - \mu_2 + \mu_3 + D_e \mu_4 - D_c \mu_5 = 0 \\ & c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^2 (\lambda - \lambda_e)^2}{(n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e))^2} - \mu_5 = 0 \\ & \frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} + \frac{n_c D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)} \leq \bar{R} \lambda \\ & \mu_1 \geq 0, \quad \mu_1 \left[\frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} + \frac{n_c D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)} - \bar{R} \lambda \right] = 0 \\ & \lambda_e > 0, \quad \mu_2 \geq 0, \quad \mu_2 \lambda_e = 0 \\ & \lambda_e < \lambda, \quad \mu_3 \geq 0, \quad \mu_3 (\lambda - \lambda_e) = 0 \\ & N_e - D_e \lambda_e > 0, \quad \mu_4 \geq 0, \quad \mu_4 (N_e - D_e \lambda_e) = 0 \\ & n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e) > 0, \quad \mu_5 \geq 0, \quad \mu_5 [n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Notice that constraints imply $\mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5 = 0$. Moreover, it follows from second equation that $\mu_1 > 0$, thus first constraint holds as an equality, i.e.,

$$\frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} + \frac{n_c D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)} = \bar{R} \lambda,$$

that is equivalent to

$$n_c = \frac{\left[\bar{R} \lambda - \frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} \right] D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)}{\bar{R} \lambda - \frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)}. \quad (40)$$

Since $\mu_1 > 0$, first equation implies that

$$\frac{D_e N_e^2}{(N_e - D_e \lambda_e)^2} = \frac{D_c n_c^2}{(n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e))^2},$$

hence

$$\frac{\sqrt{D_e} N_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} = \frac{\sqrt{D_c} n_c}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)},$$

that is equivalent to

$$n_c = \frac{\sqrt{D_e} D_c N_e (\lambda - \lambda_e)}{N_e (\sqrt{D_e} - \sqrt{D_c}) + D_e \sqrt{D_c} \lambda_e}. \quad (41)$$

It follows from (40)–(41) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{D_c} (N_e - D_e \lambda_e) \left[(N_e D_e + \bar{R} \lambda D_e - N_e \sqrt{D_c D_e}) \lambda_e \right. \\ & \quad \left. - N_e \bar{R} \lambda + N_e \lambda \sqrt{D_c D_e} \right] = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since $N_e - D_e \lambda_e > 0$, we get that the optimal edge load is

$$\lambda_e^* = \frac{N_e \lambda (\bar{R} - \sqrt{D_c D_e})}{N_e D_e + \bar{R} \lambda D_e - N_e \sqrt{D_c D_e}}.$$

Finally, we get from (40) the optimal number of cloud resources:

$$n_c^* = \frac{D_c \lambda [\bar{R} D_e \lambda - N_e (\bar{R} - D_e)]}{N_e (\sqrt{D_e} - \sqrt{D_c})^2 + D_e \lambda (\bar{R} - D_c)}.$$

□

Proof of Theorem 4.2 with the additional delay term δ_{II}/\tilde{B}

Following the very same steps of the Proof of Theorem 4.2, we obtain that the solution for the edge platform problem where no cloud resource is used is the same. If the edge resources are saturated and also cloud resources have to be used, the edge platform problem is:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{(\lambda_e, n_c)} c_c n_c \\ & \text{s.t. } \frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} + (\lambda - \lambda_e) \left[\frac{\delta_{II}}{\tilde{B}} + \frac{D_c n_c}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)} \right] \leq \bar{R} \lambda \\ & \quad 0 < \lambda_e < \lambda \\ & \quad N_e - D_e \lambda_e > 0 \\ & \quad n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e) > 0 \end{aligned}$$

By proceeding in the same way as the Proof of Theorem 4.2, the associated KKT system is the following:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D_e N_e^2}{(N_e - D_e \lambda_e)^2} - \frac{\delta_{II}}{\tilde{B}} - \frac{D_c n_c^2}{(n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e))^2} = 0, \\ \frac{D_e N_e \lambda_e}{N_e - D_e \lambda_e} + (\lambda - \lambda_e) \left(\frac{\delta_{II}}{\tilde{B}} + \frac{n_c D_c}{n_c - D_c (\lambda - \lambda_e)} \right) = \bar{R} \lambda. \end{cases}$$

The latter system of equations does not admit solutions in closed form since developing the calculations yields a fourth-degree equation.

Proof of Theorem 4.4

Proof. Let $D = |D|$, and assume, without loss of generality, $D \setminus D' = \{1, 2\}$. The minimization problem is convex and the Slater constraint qualification holds, thus the problem is equivalent to the corresponding KKT system:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_e + \mu_1 - \mu_2 \frac{D_e^{(3)^2} \lambda^{(3)}}{(n_e^{(3)} - D_e^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)})^2} - \mu_3 &= 0 \\
c_e + \mu_1 - \mu_2 \frac{D_e^{(4)^2} \lambda^{(4)}}{(n_e^{(4)} - D_e^{(4)} \lambda^{(4)})^2} - \mu_4 &= 0 \\
&\vdots \\
c_e + \mu_1 - \mu_2 \frac{D_e^{(D)^2} \lambda^{(D)}}{(n_e^{(D)} - D_e^{(D)} \lambda^{(D)})^2} - \mu_D &= 0 \\
\mu_1 (n_e^{(3)} + n_e^{(4)} + \dots + n_e^{(D)} - N_e) &= 0 \\
\mu_2 \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} \frac{D_e^{(k)} n_e^{(k)}}{n_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)}} - \bar{R} \right) &= 0 \\
\mu_3 (n_e^{(3)} - D_e^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)}) &= 0 \\
\mu_4 (n_e^{(4)} - D_e^{(4)} \lambda^{(4)}) &= 0 \\
&\vdots \\
\mu_D (n_e^{(D)} - D_e^{(D)} \lambda^{(D)}) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Constraints imply $\mu_1 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \dots = \mu_D = 0$ and $\mu_2 > 0$, thus

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} \frac{D_e^{(k)} n_e^{(k)}}{n_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)}} - \bar{R} = 0. \quad (42)$$

Moreover, it follows that the first $D-2$ equations become

$$\begin{aligned}
c_e - \mu_2 \frac{D_e^{(3)^2} \lambda^{(3)}}{(n_e^{(3)} - D_e^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)})^2} &= 0 \\
c_e - \mu_2 \frac{D_e^{(4)^2} \lambda^{(4)}}{(n_e^{(4)} - D_e^{(4)} \lambda^{(4)})^2} &= 0 \\
&\vdots \\
c_e - \mu_2 \frac{D_e^{(D)^2} \lambda^{(D)}}{(n_e^{(D)} - D_e^{(D)} \lambda^{(D)})^2} &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

from which, by isolating μ_2/c_e ,

$$\mu_2/c_e = \frac{(n_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)})^2}{D_e^{(k)^2} \lambda^{(k)}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{D}',$$

which implies the following $D-3$ equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
n_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)} &= \frac{D_e^{(k)}}{D_e^{(3)}} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda^{(k)}}{\lambda^{(3)}}} \cdot (n_e^{(3)} - D_e^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)}) \\
\forall k &= 4, \dots, D. \quad (43)
\end{aligned}$$

Solving the system of equations (42)-(43) implies

$$n_e^{(k)} = D_e^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)} + D_e^{(k)} \sqrt{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} D_e^{(m)} \sqrt{\lambda^{(m)}}}{\bar{R} - \sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} D_e^{(m)}}$$

holds for any $k \in \mathcal{D}'$. Note that in the OnlyEdge scenario all the resources are in the edge, so

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} n_e^{(k)} < N_e,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} n_e^{(k)} &= \sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} D_e^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)} \\
&+ \frac{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} D_e^{(m)} \sqrt{\lambda^{(m)}}}{\bar{R} - \sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} D_e^{(m)}} \cdot \sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} D_e^{(k)} \sqrt{\lambda^{(k)}}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of Theorem 4.5

Proof. Let $D = |\mathcal{D}|$, and assume, without loss of generality, $\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}' = \{1, 2\}$. The minimization problem is convex and the Slater constraint qualification holds, thus the problem is equivalent to the corresponding KKT system:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^{(3)^2} \lambda^{(3)}}{(n_c^{(3)} - D_c^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)})^2} - \mu_2 &= 0 \\
c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^{(4)^2} \lambda^{(4)}}{(n_c^{(4)} - D_c^{(4)} \lambda^{(4)})^2} - \mu_3 &= 0 \\
&\vdots \\
c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^{(D)^2} \lambda^{(D)}}{(n_c^{(D)} - D_c^{(D)} \lambda^{(D)})^2} - \mu_{D-1} &= 0 \\
\mu_1 \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} \left(\frac{\delta_{II}^{(k)}}{\bar{B}} + \frac{D_c^{(k)} n_c^{(k)}}{n_c^{(k)} - D_c^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)}} \right) - \bar{R} \right) &= 0 \\
\mu_2 (n_c^{(3)} - D_c^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)}) &= 0 \\
\mu_3 (n_c^{(4)} - D_c^{(4)} \lambda^{(4)}) &= 0 \\
&\vdots \\
\mu_{D-1} (n_c^{(D)} - D_c^{(D)} \lambda^{(D)}) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

Constraints imply $\mu_2 = \mu_3 = \dots = \mu_{D-1} = 0$ and $\mu_1 > 0$, thus

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}'} \left(\frac{\delta_{II}^{(k)}}{\bar{B}} + \frac{D_c^{(k)} n_c^{(k)}}{n_c^{(k)} - D_c^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)}} \right) - \bar{R} = 0. \quad (44)$$

Moreover, it follows that the first $D-2$ equations become

$$\begin{aligned}
c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^{(3)^2} \lambda^{(3)}}{(n_c^{(3)} - D_c^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)})^2} &= 0 \\
c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^{(4)^2} \lambda^{(4)}}{(n_c^{(4)} - D_c^{(4)} \lambda^{(4)})^2} &= 0 \\
&\vdots \\
c_c - \mu_1 \frac{D_c^{(D)^2} \lambda^{(D)}}{(n_c^{(D)} - D_c^{(D)} \lambda^{(D)})^2} &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

from which, by isolating μ_1/c_c , we get

$$\mu_1/c_c = \frac{(n_c^{(k)} - D_c^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)})^2}{D_c^{(k)^2} \lambda^{(k)}} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{D}',$$

which implies the following $D-3$ equations:

$$n_c^{(k)} - D_c^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)} = \frac{D_c^{(k)}}{D_c^{(3)}} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda^{(k)}}{\lambda^{(3)}}} \cdot (n_c^{(3)} - D_c^{(3)} \lambda^{(3)}) \quad \forall k = 4, \dots, D. \quad (45)$$

Solving the system of equations (44)-(45) implies

$$n_c^{(k)} = D_c^{(k)} \lambda^{(k)} + D_c^{(k)} \sqrt{\lambda^{(k)}} \cdot \frac{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} D_c^{(m)} \sqrt{\lambda^{(m)}}}{\bar{R} - \left(\sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} D_c^{(m)} + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{D}'} \frac{\delta_{II}^{(m)}}{B} \right)}$$

holds for any $k \in \mathcal{D}'$. \square

Proof of Theorem 4.6

Proof. Assuming the users' decisions $x_i^{(k)}$ are fixed given the platform profit function (17a), the only part of the platform profit function that changes with increasing r is $r^{(k)} x_i^{(k)}$, which causes an increase of the platform profit. So, in each interval in which the users' decisions are fixed, the maximum point is at the end of the interval. On the other hand, we know that users' behaviours impose the platform's profit and the behaviour of a user will change when they make a decision to participate in the MEC system or not and change the selected deployment from one to another. This behaviour changes happen only immediately before the points of discontinuity and the platform profit can increase or decrease as shown in Figure 5. Therefore, in a specific interval between two points of discontinuity where the users' decisions are fixed, the optimal solution is either obtained by decreasing the price by ϵ , by setting $r = \text{change}_{jl} - \epsilon$ or $r = \text{drop}_k - \epsilon$, if the platform profit is also increased.

Otherwise, the optimal solution in that interval is either $r = \text{change}_{jl}$ or $r = \text{drop}_k$. Accordingly, it can be concluded that the optimal platform profit will happen immediately before or exactly at these points of discontinuity. \square

Linearization of users' problem

In this section, we present the linearization of the optimality constraint (19b) related to the user-side problem.

Assume, without loss of generality, $\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}' = \{1, 2\}$ The cost for user i to run deployment k is computed as

$$C_i^{(k)} = T_i \left(\alpha_i r^{(k)} + (1 - \alpha_i) \beta_i \left(p_{I,i}^{(k)} + p_{II,i}^{(k)} \right) \lambda T_i + \zeta_i \delta_{II}^{(k)} \lambda \right), \quad (46)$$

with $\delta_{II}^{(1)} = \delta_{II}^{(2)} = 0$. Since memory and energy constraints are independent of other variables, these conditions are checked before solving the problem and embedded as binary parameter $s_i^{(k)}$ in the optimization problem. Therefore, the binary parameter $s_i^{(k)} = 1$ if user i has both enough energy and memory to run deployment k on both its smart device and phone, while $s_i^{(k)} = 0$ otherwise. The linear constraints equivalent to (19b) are the following:

$$-(1 - t_i^{(k)})M \leq U_i - C_i^{(k)} \leq t_i^{(k)}M \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{D} \quad (47)$$

$$-(1 - z_i^{(jl)})M \leq C_i^{(l)} - C_i^{(j)} \leq z_i^{(jl)}M \quad \forall j, l \in \mathcal{D}, j \neq l \quad (48)$$

$$z_i^{(jl)} + z_i^{(lj)} = 1 \quad \forall j, l \in \mathcal{D}, j \neq l \quad (49)$$

$$x_i^{(k)} \leq s_i^{(k)} t_i^{(k)} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{D} \quad (50)$$

$$x_i^{(k)} \geq s_i^{(k)} t_i^{(k)} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{D} \setminus \{k\}} s_i^{(l)} (z_i^{(kl)} - 1) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{D} \quad (51)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{D}} x_i^{(k)} \leq 1 \quad (52)$$

$$x_i^{(k)}, t_i^{(k)}, z_i^{(jl)} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k, j, l \in \mathcal{D}, j \neq l \quad (53)$$

where M is a large enough parameter, variable $t_i^{(k)}$ indicates whether $U_i \geq C_i^{(k)}(r)$ and variable $z_i^{(jl)}$ denotes if $C_i^{(j)}(r) \leq C_i^{(l)}(r)$. Note that the dependence of cost on price r makes $t_i^{(k)}$ and $z_i^{(jl)}$ variables.

Support functions of Algorithms

We report here the algorithms related to the support functions of Algorithms 4 and 5. Recall that Algorithm 4 performs the allocation of resources to the users, for a list of elite candidate solutions returned by Algorithm 3 (see Section 4.4). This allocation is done to satisfy the users' time constraints and the constraint on the maximum number of edge servers. The following procedures are used within Algorithm 4. First, the procedure MOVEUSER moves the user j who selected the deployment k , assigned to the edge ($y_j^e = 1$) and with the lowest local execution time $V_k^{(k)}$, from the edge to the cloud. Once the user assignment variables, y_i^e and y_i^c , and deployment loads, $\lambda_e^{(k)}$ and $\lambda_c^{(k)}$, have been updated (lines 2-4), the procedure recomputes the optimal number of edge servers $\bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ needed to serve the load $\lambda_e^{(k)}$ (lines 5-7). Specifically, the calculation of $\bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ is done by restricting the resource allocation problem to only the load $\lambda_e^{(k)}$, relative to deployment k . Consider, therefore, constraint (25). The optimal number of edge servers is obtained by considering as the response time of the platform (\bar{R}) the smallest residual time, LD , among those of the users who have selected deployment k and are assigned to the edge. Calculations follow:

$$\frac{D_e^{(k)} \bar{n}_e^{(k)}}{\bar{n}_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)}} = LD \quad (54)$$

$$\bar{n}_e^{(k)} = D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)} \frac{LD}{LD - D_e^{(k)}} \quad (55)$$

$\bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ is then rounded to the next integer. The procedure MOVEDEPLOYMENT moves all users who have chosen a given deployment from edge to cloud, setting the optimal number of edge servers $\bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ for that deployment to zero. COMPUTEEDGESERVERS calculates the optimal number of edge servers $\bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ for a given deployment, based on the load $\lambda_e^{(k)}$ assigned to the edge by Algorithm 3. Specifically, the procedure first calculates the *local execution time* for each user i selecting deployment k and stores it in $V_i^{(k)}$ (line 15). If Algorithm 3 allocated only edge resources to deployment k (line 16), all users are initially assigned to the edge (line 17). If the sum of the local execution time and the edge service time is less than the maximum response time \bar{R} (line 18),

the optimal number of edge resources is the one estimated by Algorithm 3 (line 19). Otherwise, the optimal number of edge servers is calculated based on the shortest residual time among the users who selected the given deployment (lines 20-23), similar to the MOVEUSER procedure. If Algorithm 3 assigned cloud resources to deployment k , users are first split between edge and cloud, assigning those with the lowest local execution time to the cloud (lines 27-31). Next, the optimal number of edge servers to satisfy the load $\lambda_e^{(k)}$ is calculated as in the previous case (lines 32-34). Finally, the procedure COMPUTECLOUDVMS calculates the optimal number of cloud VMs to satisfy the load $\lambda_c^{(k)}$ on the cloud. Similar to the edge side, the cloud VMs are calculated based on the smallest remaining time LD among the users who selected deployment k and were allocated on the cloud (lines 39-40). Note that the delay due to data transmission between edge and cloud is also considered in the calculation of LD . The final calculation is similar to (54)-(55) (line 41), substituting the cloud (subscript c) for the edge (subscript e).

Algorithm 5, follow the line, seeks a solution to the problem in the scenario with partial knowledge of user parameters. Specifically, the algorithm tries to improve the solution by moving along the lines of the platform profit function, starting from the most promising r observed, i.e., the one associated with the highest profit (see Section 4.5). Algorithm 6 serves as a support function for Algorithm 5. Given the price r and *ordering* as input, the algorithm asks the control agent for the deployment chosen by each user for that price (lines 3-4), stores the values of $x_i^{(k)}$ and computes the loads $\lambda^{(k)}$ for all deployments $k \in \mathcal{D}'$ (line 5). Subsequently, in analogy with Algorithm 3, the approximate $n_e^{(k)}, n_c^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}$ are computed by Algorithm 2 for each order. The platform profit is estimated, and the solutions are stored (lines 7-11). Finally, the best solution in terms of profit is returned (lines 12-13).

Parameters setting

The parameters settings of experiments and corresponding figures and tables are reported in this section. First, Figure 15 shows the results of profiling the YoloV4 neural network, as described in Section 5.1. Each subplot refers to a specific splitting point (the x-axis) between the phone and edge. For example, the first subplot refers to the case in which only local devices are used. The bar at each split point shows the execution time of the smart device and phone if the DNN is split at the corresponding point. As expected, the transfer times from the smart device to the phone are negligible thanks to the WiFi 7 bandwidth. Following this analysis, we selected the splitting points with the lowest total execution time to determine the deployment-dependent system parameters.

Table 4 shows the indices of the selected splitting points relative to Figure 15. Note that the first two deployments have only the smart device-phone splitting point ($\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}' = \{1, 2\}$). As for the case with $|\mathcal{D}| = 3$, only the third deployment assigns part of the computation to the edge/cloud, which means that in this scenario we solve the problem in the so-called ‘‘single deployment offloading scenario’’. Many of the parameters of the system are derived from the choice of the splitting points.

Procedures for users assignment

Move users

```

1: procedure MOVEUSER( $V^{(k)}, N^{(k)}, \bar{R}, D_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}, \lambda, y_i^e, y_i^c, \bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ )
2:    $j \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{i \in N^{(k)}, y_i^e=1} V_i^{(k)}$ 
3:    $y_j^e \leftarrow 0, y_j^c \leftarrow 1$ 
4:    $\lambda_c^{(k)} \leftarrow \lambda_c^{(k)} + \lambda, \lambda_e^{(k)} \leftarrow \lambda_e^{(k)} - \lambda$ 
5:    $j \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in N^{(k)}, y_i^e=1} V_i^{(k)}$ 
6:    $LD \leftarrow \bar{R} - V_j^{(k)}$ 
7:    $\bar{n}_e^{(k)} \leftarrow \lceil D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)} \frac{LD}{LD - D_e^{(k)}} \rceil$ 
8: end procedure

```

Move deployments

```

9: procedure MOVEDEPLOYMENT( $N^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}, y_i^e, y_i^c, \bar{n}_e^{(k)}$ )
10:   $y_i^e \leftarrow 0, y_i^c \leftarrow 1, \forall i \in N^{(k)}$ 
11:   $\lambda_c^{(k)} \leftarrow \lambda_c^{(k)} + \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)} \leftarrow 0$ 
12:   $\bar{n}_e^{(k)} \leftarrow 0$ 
13: end procedure

```

Compute edge servers

```

14: procedure COMPUTEEDGESERVERS( $V^{(k)}, N^{(k)}, \bar{R}, D_{j,i}^{(k)}, \delta_j^{(k)}, \bar{B}_i, B_i, D_e^{(k)}, n_e^{(k)}, n_c^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}, y_i^e, y_i^c, \bar{n}_e^{(k)}, \bar{n}_c^{(k)}$ )
15:   $V_i^{(k)} = D_{I,i}^{(k)} + \frac{\delta_i^{(k)}}{B_i} + D_{II,i}^{(k)} + \frac{\delta_{II,i}^{(k)}}{B_i}, \forall i \in N^{(k)}$ 
16:  if  $n_c^{(k)} = 0$  then
17:     $y_i^e \leftarrow 1, \forall i \in N^{(k)}$ 
18:    if  $V_i^{(k)} + \frac{n_e^{(k)} D_e^{(k)}}{n_e^{(k)} - D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)}} \leq \bar{R} \forall i \in N^{(k)}$  then
19:       $\bar{n}_e^{(k)} \leftarrow n_e^{(k)}$ 
20:    else
21:       $j \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in N^{(k)}} V_i^{(k)}$ 
22:       $LD \leftarrow \bar{R} - V_j^{(k)}$ 
23:       $\bar{n}_e^{(k)} \leftarrow \lceil D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)} \frac{LD}{LD - D_e^{(k)}} \rceil$ 
24:    end if
25:  end if
26:  if  $n_c^{(k)} > 0$  then
27:    sort the users by  $V_i^{(k)}$  increasingly
28:     $\lambda^{(k)} \leftarrow \lambda_e^{(k)} + \lambda_c^{(k)}$ 
29:     $j \leftarrow \frac{\lambda_c^{(k)}}{\lambda} + 1$ 
30:     $y_i^c \leftarrow 1, \forall i \in N^{(k)} : i < j$ 
31:     $y_i^e \leftarrow 1, \forall i \in N^{(k)} : i \geq j$ 
32:     $j \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in N^{(k)}} V_i^{(k)}$ 
33:     $LD \leftarrow \bar{R} - V_j^{(k)}$ 
34:     $\bar{n}_e^{(k)} \leftarrow \lceil D_e^{(k)} \lambda_e^{(k)} \frac{LD}{LD - D_e^{(k)}} \rceil$ 
35:  end if
36: end procedure

```

Compute cloud VMs

```

37: procedure COMPUTECLOUDVMS( $V^{(k)}, N^{(k)}, \bar{R}, \delta_{II}^{(k)}, \bar{B}, D_c^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}, y_i^c, \bar{n}_c^{(k)}$ )
38:  if  $\lambda_c^{(k)} > 0$  then
39:     $j \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in N^{(k)}, y_i^c=1} V_i^{(k)}$ 
40:     $LD \leftarrow \bar{R} - (V_j^{(k)} + \frac{\delta_{II}^{(k)}}{\bar{B}})$ 
41:     $\bar{n}_c^{(k)} \leftarrow \lceil D_c^{(k)} \lambda_c^{(k)} \frac{LD}{LD - D_c^{(k)}} \rceil$ 
42:  end if
43: end procedure

```

Number of dep.	Dep. 1	Dep. 2	Dep. 3	Dep. 4	Dep. 5
$ \mathcal{D} = 3$	3, -	1, -	1, 3		
$ \mathcal{D} = 4$	3, -	1, -	1, 13	1, 3	
$ \mathcal{D} = 5$	3, -	1, -	4, 13	1, 13	1, 3

Table 4: Selected splitting points for different number of deployments in the form *first splitting point, second splitting point*.

Once the deployment indices have been set, we can define all the parameters of the MEC system. In particular, Table 5 shows the settings for system parameters,

Figure 15: Execution time of a YOLOv4 neural network.

Algorithm 6 User Request and Profit Estimate

- 1: **Input:** $r, r_0, \gamma^{(k)}, \lambda, ordering$
 - 2: **Initialization:** $Solutions \leftarrow \emptyset$
 - 3: $r^{(k)} \leftarrow r_0 + \gamma^{(k)} r \forall k \in \mathcal{D}'$
 - 4: $x \leftarrow$ Ask for chosen deployment given r
 - 5: $\lambda^{(k)} \leftarrow \sum_{i \in \mathcal{U}} \lambda x_i^{(k)} \forall k \in \mathcal{D}'$
 - 6: $orders \leftarrow$ Compute orders given $ordering$
 - 7: **for** $order$ **in** $orders$ **do**
 - 8: $n_e^{(k)}, n_c^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)} \leftarrow$ OPTIMALRESOURCENUMBERS($order, \lambda^{(k)}, N_e$)
 - 9: $P \leftarrow$ Compute platform profit given $r, x, n_e^{(k)}, n_c^{(k)}$
 - 10: $append(P, r, x, n_e^{(k)}, n_c^{(k)}, \lambda_e^{(k)}, \lambda_c^{(k)}, order)$ to $Solutions$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: **sort** $Solutions$ by P decreasingly
 - 13: **return** the first element of $Solutions$
-

including the number of users, the number of available edge servers, the average response time, execution time, and memory required per deployment, platform costs, and data size transferred between devices. Table 6 defines user parameters such as energy consumption and data transfer costs, execution times on local devices, power consumed when launching the application with a given deployment, application utilisation times, energy and memory available on devices.

Finally, Table 7 presents the fine-tuned parameters used in Algorithm 5 to achieve the results discussed in Section 5.5.1. These parameters, described in Section 4.5, were selected based on a grid search involving *Cutting fraction*, ϵ *scale* and *Fraction of initial points*, with the initial value of *Fraction of total points* set to 0.1. The search considered both possibilities of *First points approach* separately. It's worth noting that the sensitivity analysis in Section 5.5.2 demonstrates that while the the performance of the algorithm is robust against parameter variations, fine-tuning enhances its stability across different scenarios.

Experimental results

This section presents tables related to the experimental results discussed in Section 5. Tables 8, 9 and 10 depict the performance evaluation of the heuristic algorithm under full knowledge of users' parameters compared to the global solver BARON. Table 8 shows the profit ratio of the heuristic algorithm with the chosen order and that of BARON compared to the combinatorial heuristic algorithm. The "BARON solutions" column indicates the percentage of times BARON returns a feasible (not necessarily the best) solution within a maximum of two hours across 10 instances. The results indicate that for more than 100 users, the average profit of BARON is lower than that of the heuristic algorithm. This is due to its inability to converge to the optimal solution within the given time frame, and it sometimes fails to find a feasible solution for 200 users. Table 9 compares the execution times of the heuristic algorithm with that of BARON (limited to a maximum time of two hours), and shows in the column "BARON converged" the percentage of times BARON converges to the optimal solution (i.e., the times in which the solver stops before the maximum time set). BARON struggles to converge for more than 100 users, whereas the heuristic algorithm always returns the solution in less than one second (at most 0.25 seconds with the chosen order). To assess the optimality of the heuristic solutions, Table 10 compares the profits and convergence rates of BARON when initialized with solutions from the combinatorial algorithm. Specifically, the first column shows the profit ratio between the final solution returned by the global solver and that of the combinatorial algorithm. The second column reports the percentage of times the solver converges within two hours, while the last column indicates the percentage of cases where the solution returned by BARON is better than that of the heuristic algorithm. The results indicate that the solution returned

System Parameters	
N	In range (50, 1000)
λ	Uniform distribution in [2, 4] req/s
N_e	$\frac{N}{20}$
$D_e^{(k)}$	D = 3: $D_e^{(3)} = 0.23$ s D = 4: $D_e^{(3)} = 0.12$ s, $D_e^{(4)} = 0.23$ s D = 5: $D_e^{(3)} = 0.12$ s, $D_e^{(4)} = 0.12$ s, $D_e^{(5)} = 0.23$ s
$D_c^{(k)}$	$\frac{5}{6} D_e^{(k)} \forall k \in \mathcal{D}'$
$m_g^{(k)}$	$5 - 4 \frac{k}{ \mathcal{D} }$ MB $\forall k \in \mathcal{D}$
$m_p^{(k)}$	$5 - 4 \frac{k}{ \mathcal{D} }$ MB $\forall k \in \mathcal{D}$
\bar{R}	Uniform distribution in [2.75, 3.25] s
T	3600 s
c_c	Uniform distribution in [1, 2] \$/h
c_e	0.20 c_c
$\gamma^{(k)}$	$\gamma^{(1)} = \gamma^{(2)} = 0, \gamma^{(3)} = 1, \gamma^{(k)} = \frac{D_c^{(k)}}{D_c^{(k-1)}} \gamma^{(k-1)}, \text{ for } k = 4, \dots, \mathcal{D} $
ϵ	1×10^{-18}
$PopSize$	$10 * \text{orders} $
\tilde{B}	Uniform distribution in [9216, 10240] Mbps
$\delta_{gp}^{(k)}$	D = 3: $\delta_{gp}^{(1)} = 2.64$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(2)} = 5.28$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(3)} = 5.28$ MB D = 4: $\delta_{gp}^{(1)} = 2.64$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(2)} = 5.28$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(3)} = 5.28$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(4)} = 5.28$ MB D = 5: $\delta_{gp}^{(1)} = 2.64$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(2)} = 5.28$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(3)} = 2.64$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(4)} = 5.28$ MB, $\delta_{gp}^{(5)} = 5.28$ MB
$\delta_{pe}^{(k)}$	D = 3: $\delta_{pe}^{(3)} = 2.64$ MB D = 4: $\delta_{pe}^{(3)} = 0.66$ MB, $\delta_{pe}^{(4)} = 2.64$ MB D = 5: $\delta_{pe}^{(3)} = 0.66$ MB, $\delta_{pe}^{(4)} = 0.66$ MB, $\delta_{pe}^{(5)} = 2.64$ MB
r_0	Uniform in $[8.30 \times 10^{-4}, 8.35 \times 10^{-4}]$ \$/s
r_{min}	5.56×10^{-4} \$/s
r_{max}	3×10^{-3} \$/s
M	100

Table 5: System parameters setting.

User Parameters	
$D_{g,i}^{(k)}$	D = 3: $D_{g,i}^{(1)} = 0.19$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(2)} = 0.10$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(3)} = 0.10$ s D = 4: $D_{g,i}^{(1)} = 0.19$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(2)} = 0.10$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(3)} = 0.10$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(4)} = 0.10$ s D = 5: $D_{g,i}^{(1)} = 0.19$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(2)} = 0.10$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(3)} = 0.21$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(4)} = 0.10$ s, $D_{g,i}^{(5)} = 0.10$ s
$D_{p,i}^{(k)}$	D = 3: $D_{p,i}^{(1)} = 0.23$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(2)} = 0.28$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(3)} = 0.57$ s D = 4: $D_{p,i}^{(1)} = 0.23$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(2)} = 0.28$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(3)} = 0.16$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(4)} = 0.06$ s D = 5: $D_{p,i}^{(1)} = 0.23$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(2)} = 0.28$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(3)} = 0.11$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(4)} = 0.16$ s, $D_{p,i}^{(5)} = 0.06$ s
$p_{g,i}^{(k)}$	$p_{g,i}^{(k)} = D_{g,i}^{(k)}$ W $\forall k \in \mathcal{D}$
$p_{p,i}^{(k)}$	$p_{p,i}^{(k)} = 40 D_{p,i}^{(k)}$ W $\forall k \in \mathcal{D}$
\bar{B}_i	Uniform distribution in [9.6, 46.1] Gbps
B_i	Uniform distribution in [9.9, 25.1] Mbps
$\bar{E}_{g,i}$	Uniform distribution in $[\min_k 0.9\lambda T_i^2 p_{g,i}^{(k)}, \max_k 1.2\lambda T_i^2 p_{g,i}^{(k)}]$ J
$\bar{E}_{p,i}$	Uniform distribution in $[\min_k 0.9\lambda T_i^2 p_{p,i}^{(k)}, \max_k 1.2\lambda T_i^2 p_{p,i}^{(k)}]$ J
$\bar{M}_{g,i}$	Uniform distribution in $[5 \mathcal{D} , 6 \mathcal{D}]$ MB
$\bar{M}_{p,i}$	Uniform distribution in $[5 \mathcal{D} , 6 \mathcal{D}]$ MB
T_i	50% of users uniform distribution in [540, 660] s, 50% of users uniform distribution in [1080, 1320] s
β_i	Uniform distribution in [0.49, 0.52] \$/kWh
α_i	Energy dependent: $0.5 + 0.3 \min \left(\frac{\bar{E}_{g,i} - \min_k 0.9\lambda T_i^2 p_{g,i}^{(k)}}{\max_k 1.2\lambda T_i^2 p_{g,i}^{(k)} - \min_k 0.9\lambda T_i^2 p_{g,i}^{(k)}}, \frac{\bar{E}_{p,i} - \min_k 0.9\lambda T_i^2 p_{p,i}^{(k)}}{\max_k 1.2\lambda T_i^2 p_{p,i}^{(k)} - \min_k 0.9\lambda T_i^2 p_{p,i}^{(k)}} \right)$
ζ_i	Fixed: 0.65, Random: uniform in [0.5, 0.75]
U_i	Uniform distribution in $[5.3 \times 10^{-5}, 6.0 \times 10^{-5}]$ \$/MB
U_i	Uniform distribution in [8, 12] \$/h

Table 6: Users parameters setting.

by the combinatorial algorithm is improved in up to 20% of cases. On average, the highest improvement is observed in the scenario with 25 users and 4 deployments, where BARON achieves an average profit improvement of 1.66%.

Follow the line approach parameters	
Cutting fraction cut	0.1
First points approach	Equispaced
ϵ_{scale}	2
Fraction of initial points η_{init}	0.06
Fraction of total points η_{tot}	0.1

Table 7: Fine-tuned configuration of the Follow the line algorithm.

N	Profit ratio Chosen order (%)			Profit ratio BARON (%)			BARON solutions (%)		
	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$
10	0.00	-1.07	-1.77	-0.07	1.34	0.00	100	100	100
25	0.00	-2.65	-2.77	0.40	1.66	-0.03	100	100	100
50	0.00	-0.70	-1.22	0.77	0.02	0.07	100	80	100
100	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.42	-2.94	-7.24	100	100	100
200	0.00	-0.06	0.00	-3.92	-6.53	-9.64	80	30	70

Table 8: Performance of the heuristic algorithm and BARON without initialization.

N	Execution time Combinatorial (s)			Execution time Chosen order (s)			Execution time BARON (s)			BARON converged (%)		
	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$
10	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.04	821.31	37.01	339.60	90	100	100
25	0.05	0.10	0.13	0.05	0.09	0.09	2895.69	3151.19	2665.85	60	70	70
50	0.10	0.13	0.18	0.10	0.11	0.10	5777.92	6419.36	6559.40	20	20	10
100	0.13	0.18	0.29	0.12	0.16	0.17	6891.10	7205.66	7207.90	10	0	0
200	0.18	0.29	0.51	0.18	0.23	0.25	7207.03	7213.40	7221.31	0	0	0

Table 9: Performance of the heuristic algorithm and BARON without initialization.

N	Profit ratio BARON initialized (%)			BARON initialized converged (%)			Initial solution improved (%)		
	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$	$ \mathcal{D} =3$	$ \mathcal{D} =4$	$ \mathcal{D} =5$
10	0.32	1.34	0.00	100	100	100	20	20	10
25	0.35	1.66	0.00	100	100	90	10	20	0
50	0.79	0.23	0.17	100	80	100	10	10	20
100	0.00	0.00	0.29	100	90	90	0	0	20
200	0.00	0.00	0.00	100	100	90	0	0	0

Table 10: Performance of BARON with initialization.